

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 47

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 47:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of the sons of Korah.</p>	<p>לְמִנְצֵחַ לְבְנֵי-קָרַח Psa. 47:1</p>
<p>Psa. 47:1 O “clap your hands, all peoples; ^bShout to God with the voice of ¹joy. ² For the LORD Most High is to be ^afeared, A ^bgreat King over all the earth. ³ He ^asubdues peoples under us And nations under our feet. ⁴ He chooses our ^ainheritance for us, The ^bglory of Jacob whom He loves. ¹Selah.</p>	<p>מִזְמוֹר : ² כָּל-הָעַמִּים תִּקְעוּ-כַף תְּרִיעוּ לֵאלֹהִים בְּקוֹל רִנָּה : ³ כִּי-יְהוָה עֲלִינוּ נֹרָא מֶלֶךְ יָדוּל עַל-כָּל- הָאָרֶץ : ⁴ יְדַבֵּר עַמִּים תַּחֲתֵינוּ וְלֵאמִים תַּחַת רַגְלֵינוּ : ⁵ יִבְחַר-לָנוּ אֶת- נַחֲלָתָנוּ אֶת גְּאוֹן יַעֲקֹב אֲשֶׁר-אָהַב סִלָּה : ⁶ עָלָה אֱלֹהִים בַּתְּרוּעָה יְהוָה בְּקוֹל שׁוֹפָר : ⁷ זָמְרוּ אֱלֹהִים זָמְרוּ זָמְרוּ לְמִלְכֵנוּ זָמְרוּ : ⁸ כִּי מֶלֶךְ כָּל-הָאָרֶץ אֱלֹהִים זָמְרוּ מִשְׁכִּיל : ⁹ מֶלֶךְ אֱלֹהִים עַל-גּוֹיִם אֱלֹהִים יָשָׁב אַעֲלֵ-כִסֵּא קִדְשׁוֹ : ¹⁰ נְדִיבֵי עַמִּים אֶנְאֲסָפוּ עִם אֱלֹהֵי אַבְרָהָם כִּי לֵאלֹהִים מִגְּבֵי-אָרֶץ מְאֹד נִעְלָה :</p>
<p>Psa. 47:5 God has ^aascended ¹with a shout, The LORD, ¹with the ^bsound of a trumpet. ⁶ “Sing praises to God, sing praises; Sing praises to ^bour King, sing praises. ⁷ For God is the ^aKing of all the earth; Sing praises ^bwith a ¹skillful psalm. ⁸ God ^areigns over the nations, God ¹sits on ^bHis holy throne. ⁹ The ¹princes of the people have assembled themselves <i>as</i> the ^bpeople of the God of Abraham, For the ^cshields of the earth belong to God; He ²is ^ahighly exalted.</p>	

References

<p>Psalm 47:1 ¹Or <i>a ringing cry</i> ^aPs 98:8 ^bPs 106:47</p> <p>Psalm 47:2 ^aDeut 7:21; Neh 1:5; Ps 66:3, 5; 68:35 ^bMal 1:14</p> <p>Psalm 47:3 ^aPs 18:47</p> <p>Psalm 47:4 ¹<i>Selah</i> may mean: <i>Pause, Crescendo or Musical interlude</i> ^a1 Pet 1:4 ^bAmos 6:8; 8:7; Nah 2:2</p> <p>Psalm 47:5 ¹Or <i>amid</i> ^aPs 68:18 ^bPs 98:6</p> <p>Psalm 47:6 ^aPs 68:4 ^bPs 89:18</p> <p>Psalm 47:7 ¹Heb <i>Maskil</i> ^aZech 14:9 ^b1 Cor 14:15</p> <p>Psalm 47:8 ¹Or <i>has taken His seat</i> ^a1 Chr 16:31; Ps 22:28 ^bPs 97:2</p>	<p>Psalm 47:9 ¹Or <i>nobles</i> ²<i>Lit has greatly exalted Himself</i> ^aPs 72:11; 102:22; Is 49:7, 23 ^bRom 4:11, 12 ^cPs 89:18 ^dPs 97:9</p>
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Targum

Psa. 47:1 For praise, by the sons of Korah, a psalm. ² All you peoples, clap hands in joy, shout in the presence of the LORD with the sound of praise. ³ For the LORD Most High is to be feared, a great king over all the earth. ⁴ He will slay the peoples by plague instead of us, and he will subdue the nations under our feet. ⁵ He will favor us to inherit our heritage, the sanctuary of Jacob whom he loves forever. ⁶ Let the LORD be exalted with a shout, the LORD with the sound of the trumpet. ⁷ Sing praise in the presence of the LORD, sing praise; sing praise to our king, sing praise! ⁸ For the LORD is king over all inhabitants of the earth; sing praise before him with good understanding. ⁹ The LORD is king over the peoples; the LORD sits on his holy throne. ¹⁰ The leaders of the Gentiles have gathered, the Gentiles who believe in the God of Abraham, for in the presence of the LORD they are the shields of the earth; he has been greatly exalted.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

This Psalm is a sequel to the previous one, which describes the defeat of the nations who united against the LORD and His chosen people. The ability of the shofar blast to inspire people is a part of this Psalm, and it invokes the LORD's mercy through Chesed. On Rosh Hashannah, this Psalm is recited seven times before the sounding of the shofar.

The sages teach that there are forty-nine levels of spiritual impurity before one reaches the lowest depth of Sheol. Correspondingly there are forty-nine levels of sanctity that one can obtain. Forty-nine times on Rosh Hashannah, the LORD's name is recited, which alludes to the power of this Psalm to transform the forty-nine possible levels of spiritual uncleanness into the forty-nine corresponding levels of sanctity and purity.¹

Superscript

This Psalm proclaims how the historical events of Israel inspire all the other nations to do homage to the LORD.

To the Sefirah Netzach, a Psalm by the sons of Korach.

¹ https://www.chabad.org/library/article_cdo/aid/3680881/jewish/How-49-and-49-Equal-49.htm. Accessed 5/14/2022.

Verse one

תִּקְעוּ-כַף (teek'oo kaf) – means “clap your hands.” This phrase usually refers to a handclasp implying an obligation like giving a promise.

הִרְיֵעוּ לֵאלֹהִים (hareeoo lealohim) – means “shout to God.” This phrase calls for a powerful sound because it refers to the LORD. It also denotes the tribute to the LORD paid by the human spirit deeply moved by the thought of His overwhelming greatness.

Clasp hands, all your peoples, call forth to God the tribute loudly with rejoicing.

Verse Two

The LORD is a great ruler to be revered even as He proves to be near us through the Shekinah. His loving-kindness through the Sefirah Chesed can be found everywhere. Blessings from the LORD come to people who follow His Laws.

For the LORD who loves all things is the Most High and must be revered for all things.

Verses three & four

There is the belief that all the people of the world will eventually come together with the nation of Israel to worship the LORD.

He gathers the people together beneath us and nations under our feet.

He chooses our inheritance for us, the pride of Jacob, which He loves.

Meditate upon this verse.

Verse five

The LORD will reveal himself to other nations once those nations have obeyed the summons and once the minds of the countries come to know God. He will then reveal himself to them.

When God has ascended amidst a shout, He will appear as God, all-merciful with the sound of the shofar.

Verses six & seven

Therefore sing, sing praises to God, sing praises to our King, sing praises.

For God is the King of all the earth, sing to spread this knowledge far and wide.

Verses eight and nine

God reigns over the nations; God sits on His holy throne.

The princes of the people have assembled themselves *as* the people of the God of Abraham, For the shields of the earth belong to God; He is highly exalted.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach, a Psalm by the sons of Korach.

Clasp hands, all your peoples, call forth to God the tribute loudly with rejoicing.

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Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

